

IMPACT OF COVID-19 PANDEMIC ON ACADEMIC, SOCIAL AND MENTAL ASPECTS OF COLLEGE STUDENTS OF DISTRICT SRINAGAR OF KASHMIR

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ABSTRACT

The current research explains the impact of the COVID-19 Pandemic on academic, social, and mental aspects of college students. The outbreak of this Pandemic has propelled the whole planet to the brink of complete destruction, as the entire humanity has been significantly impacted, resulting in a large number of life moments being snatched. The aim of this research was to see how the COVID-19 Pandemic lockdown has affected students' studies, personal interactions, and mental wellbeing. For data collection, an online survey was conducted. While conducting this study, it was discovered that prolonged lockdown has had a significant impact on college students' mental health, jeopardising their ability to receive a quality education. In conclusion, this state of lockdown has caused significant problems in the lives of students, as shown by the burden that online educational approaches have put on them: many hours of work and difficulties due to a lack of physical interaction or challenges posed by mixing personal and professional lives.

Keywords: Academic, Social, Mental, Students, COVID-19.

INTRODUCTION COVID-19 has ushered us into a new world. Presumably, COVID-19 has engulfed all aspects of life, including physical, mental, social, academic, farming, accounting, clinical, broad communications, and travel industries. Data from recent public opinion polls showed that across the 28 nations surveyed, two-thirds (65%) on average say that things in their country are on the wrong track. This obscured and undetectable infection has been the best case scenario and it has resulted in serious mental and social consequences for students. The virus increases the likelihood of people experiencing human emotions such as fear (Asmundson and Taylor, 2020), concern, panic, anxiety, or depression-related distress (Bao et al., 2020). The mental and social impact of the COVID-19 Pandemic on people is most likely a truly significant, but clearly unnoticed, issue. According to the United Nation's Educational, Scientific, and Cultural Organization (UNESCO), more than 1.5 billion students and youth around the world (129 countries) have been affected by school and university closures as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic. This is a critical time for the education sector, as board exams, nursery school admissions, university entrance exams, and competitive examinations are all held during this time. Switching to the virtual method of learning has displayed restlessness, disturbance, antagonism and social viciousness. The pandemic has transformed the centuries-old chalk-talk teaching model to the one driven by technology, but a handful of private schools and government schools could

adopt online teaching methods as most institutions do not have access to e-learning solutions. At the same time, because of the innovation, contrasted with other age groups, youngsters can be uncovered to negative streams brought about by the COVID-19 plague far and wide through the web and online media. This situation may be said to make teenagers more psychologically dangerous than other age groups. Furthermore, young people are thought to have emotional outcomes such as gloom, outrage, negativity, and misery. According to a research paper published by Texthelp and educational analyst ImpactEd, teachers have experienced higher levels of distress due to the workload generated during the lockdown since March 2020. However, the unplanned shift to online learning, particularly in underdeveloped countries like India where the educational system was not prepared for online learning and the curriculum was not designed for such a format, has created the risk of most of our students becoming passive learners and losing interest due to low levels of attention span. Also, online learning is a special kind of methodology and not all teachers are good at it, or at least not all of them were ready for this sudden transition from face to-face learning to online learning. Thus, most of the teachers are just conducting lectures on video platforms such as Zoom, which may not be real online learning in the absence of a dedicated online platform specifically designed for the purpose. There is a risk of not achieving the learning outcomes. Al-Rabiaah et al. (2020) in their study on the relationship between Middle East Respiratory Syndrome-Corona Virus-MERS pandemics and stress in university students concluded that (77%) of the students exhibited low while (18.4%) showed medium level of anxiety. Likewise, Wang and others (2020) found that young people are more affected by the epidemic psychologically and feel more stressed, anxious, intolerant, and depressed in their study in which they investigated the psychological effects of the COVID-19 epidemic in China (Wang et al. 2020).

REVIEW

- Jean (2020) discussed in his paper that both teachers and students are unprepared in terms of technology handling or accessibility issues for online learning where most of the academic activities happens via zoom or Google meet without any dedicated online learning platform.
- Frkert et.al, (2020) in their study strongly that academic loss and fear of future due to Pandemic triggered children and adolescents towards suicidal attempts.
- Ozer (2020) in his study revealed that social distancing due to COVID19 may cause negative psychological conditions such as anxiety and fear which in turn affect the well-being of students. Billions of students have been affected by closure of schools and other restrictions.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The present study is stated as:

Impact of COVID-19 Pandemic on Academic, Social and Mental Aspects of College Students of

District Srinagar of Kashmir

OBJECTIVES

The objectives formulated for the present study are:

1. To study the impact of COVID-19 on academics of college students.
2. To study the impact of COVID-19 on social life of college students.
3. To study the impact of COVID-19 on mental health of college students.

TOOL

To collect data, a self-created questionnaire with three dimensions, namely social, academic, and mental health, was used. The questionnaire reflects content and face validity. The reliability coefficient is .70 and .68 estimated through test retest and split half methods respectively.

METHODOLOGY

For the present study Descriptive online survey method was used.

SAMPLE

The questionnaire was distributed to 120 B.A/B.Sc/B.Com final year students enrolled in colleges in the district Srinagar of Kashmir Province for the current study, but only 60 completed it. The data was collected by adopting the incidental sampling technique through online mode.

DATA ANALYSIS

The data collected has been analysed by using percentage statistics.

INTERPRETATION AND DISCUSSION

IMPACT OF COVID-19 PANDEMIC ON ACADEMICS

The image of the education sector is hastily changing due to the occurrence of COVID19. Significant changes have been made due to this virus. Education can occur anywhere, but its focus should be on its quality; a physically and emotionally safe environment plays an important role in the learning process. Quality education instils creativity and innovation in society, while also benefiting the nation's economy. This paper seeks to discover if the quality of education affects the different dimensions of college students or not. The data gathered for this study reveals that switching to the e-learning process reduces educational quality, as (91%) respondents believed that e-learning resulted in students' SGPA increasing without knowing much about the content and (84%) respondents strongly agreed that the risk of cheating and lenient marking is at its peak while assessing and evaluating student performance through e-learning. while a meagre section of respondents (9%) disagreed that quality education is at stake due to the Covid19 pandemic as they credited parents for being supportive. Successful attempts to increase parental involvement have taken place to provide quality education.

Covid19 lockdown leads us to stay home and do work from home, which in-turn leads towards home-schooling and enhancement in the use of digital learning. Home schooling is a progressive

educational movement in which children are educated at home rather than in schools. Teachers are using different platforms from Microsoft and Google and conferencing apps like zoom to deliver lessons for their students. According to the data, (80%) of respondents agreed that zoom meeting fatigue and stress are common among students because they find it difficult to concentrate on a single voice for an extended period of time by being passive listeners and also complained about acute back pain while sitting in front of a laptop for 4-6 hours straight. Use of technological inventions has revolutionized all fields of life, including education. The main sources in our traditional education used to be school, teachers and print media only. With new inventions and discoveries, our teaching learning process becomes interesting.

When the teaching learning process is accomplished with effective use of technology to strengthen students, that is digital learning. The data showed that 81% of respondents agreed that replacement of face-to-face learning activities enhances the knowledge about the digital world. According to the data on internet connectivity, the majority of respondents (86%) agreed that issues related to internet connectivity, limited data, and a lack of resources are like a heavy burden of work but slow delivery, while 7% of respondents were unable to provide any opinion on internet connectivity because they do not have smart phones, and 7% disagreed. Individual differences should be linked with the goals of education, curriculum, and teaching methods, taking into account the various abilities and traits of individuals, but this study revealed that by adopting online teaching/learning methods, individual differences have been greatly neglected as eye to eye contact with students is missing, as the survey conducted for this study revealed that (84%) of. Self-confidence is an attitude that allows people to have positive experiences, but (80%) of respondents agreed that e-learning activities are solely academic, with no emphasis on co-curricular activities. The data revealed that the (60%) respondents agreed that respondents become lazy by following the guidelines regarding studying from home.

IMPACT OF COVID-19 PANDEMIC ON SOCIAL LIFE

Recreation is any form of play, amusement, or relaxation used for a purpose, such as games, sports, or hobbies. The data shows that (95%) respondents do firmly believe that COVID19 plays a major role in getting addicted to social chatting apps like Whatsapp, Facebook, Snapchat, Instagram etc. Social networking has been shown to be associated with both physical and psychological well-being and (60%) respondents' experienced "cooking" as a stress reliever in lockdown. They want some distraction from the routine either at work or at home, they wish to have different, informal kinds of social interaction, and they desire to get relieved from work stress and anxieties. As the Greek philosopher Aristotle reminds us, man is a "social animal," unable to live apart from others. (82%) respondents' experience that being isolated from society while being affected by the SARS-CoV-2 virus, and the fear of transmitting it to loved ones, are prone to depression, which affects an individual's mental wellbeing in the long run.

IMPACT OF COVID-19 PANDEMIC ON MENTAL HEALTH

Further, this study disclosed that in Covid-19 lockdown the prevalence of DSPS-Delayed Sleep

Phase Syndrome-among college going students is (64%), which makes it hard to fall asleep at a conventional bedtime. Imprisonment due to Covid-19 lockdown leads respondents of this study (96%) to hopelessness, despair and apprehension and in comparison to this (64%) of respondents revealed that during Covid-19 confinement leads to tendencies of suicide. Similarly, (91%) respondents of this study experienced that they are not able to manage their time more efficiently at home, which fuels their aggression. Capriciousness due to Covid19 lockdown in the respondents of this study is found to be (68%) as they experience a constant low mood and loss of interest in activities and events that they previously enjoyed, but at the same time, they get motivated by self-counselling which elevates their mood. Mental unsoundness is to be found among respondents approximately (89%), they have some risk of developing a mental health disorder, and almost everyone in this study is suffering from PTSD-Post Traumatic Stress Disorder.

CONCLUSION

The COVID 19 pandemic has greatly affected the academic, social and psychological wellbeing of individuals, especially of students all over the world. To a significant degree, the educational sector has been disrupted. The emergence of this pandemic has completely altered the situation. Work From Home is the latest norm these days, and it has forced the world to rethink the whole culture, whether it is for the better or for the worse, whether it's transportation, business & trade, tourism, the industrial sector, or education. It has fully transformed the physical education scene into home-schooling. Students all over the world are taught online, implying that they are fully reliant on electronic devices. According to the findings, the majority of college students spend the majority of their time on social chatting apps like Whatsapp, Instagram, and Facebook because they believe them to be stress relievers. The respondents to this study believe that transitioning entirely to electronic learning has jeopardised educational quality, and they are dissatisfied with the way the government is dealing with the issue through online classes via Zoom or Google Meet. The key explanation respondents find out is that of dysfunctional internet access problems, which provokes them towards violence, mood swings, depression, and anxiety towards their future goals. The respondents also shared their thoughts about how a teacher/educator should determine a student's comprehension level during online classes because eye-to-eye interaction is not possible, and as a result, individual variations are ignored, leaving little time for other co-curricular activities. Students also reported that the risk of cheating and lenient marking is at an all-time high in online mode. The self-confidence and ability of (85%) of respondents were harmed as a result of the extended lockdown and online lessons, while (81%) believed that their digital skills had improved. Many respondents blame social isolation for their depression, and some have noticed a shift in their sleeping habits. A significant number of respondents recognise that they are suffering from post-traumatic stress disorder, which leads to acts of aggression and suicidal ideation. It's being said that he who opens a school door, closes a prison and there is hope that doors will be opened soon.

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